

Impact of Liquidity Pool Size on Trading Volume in BTC-ETH Pools

Matias Vizcaino (avizcaino3) — Walter Jack Simmons (wsimmons35) — Vítor de Matos Castilho (vcastilho3)

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Abstract

This paper investigates the dynamics of BTC-ETH liquidity pools on the Uniswap decentralized exchange, with a specific emphasis on the relationship between liquidity pool size and cumulative trading volume. Using an ordinary least squares regression model with lagged explanatory variables, we analyze the activity in the WBTC-WETH 3000 and 500 tick pools on Uniswap v3. We employ a data-driven approach, engineering features from Uniswap and Etherscan data, and take into account spillover effects from the Binance centralized exchange. Our findings confirm a direct correlation between liquidity pool size, increased mint frequency, immediate trading volumes, and cumulative trading volume. We also identify a significant spillover effect from centralized exchange activity on decentralized exchange pools. These insights offer important strategic guidance for liquidity providers, traders, and architects of decentralized exchanges. However, the potential multicollinearity of features and a predominantly linear modeling assumption call for caution in interpretation. Future work should consider employing nonlinear models and exploring other factors such as price divergences, impermanent loss, and inherent risk factors.

Introduction

Decentralized Finance (DeFi) has rapidly evolved into a crucial segment of the blockchain ecosystem, contributing significantly to the democratization of financial services. At its core, DeFi is governed by a network of decentralized exchanges (DEXs), such as Uniswap, which rely extensively on liquidity pools for the efficient operation of trading activities. Liquidity pools, empowered by an automated market maker model, are one of the vital cogs in the DeFi machine, underpinning the entire transaction mechanism on these platforms[8, 4, 12].

Given the centrality of liquidity pools in the DeFi landscape, understanding their dynamics and operational parameters is crucial. Notably, the WBTC-WETH liquidity pools on Uniswap serve as a significant focus, due to the considerable trading volume and liquidity they command. Therefore, this study delves into the exploration of these liquidity pools, investigating their intrinsic dynamics and external influences.

This study investigates these pools, specifically how pool size affects trading volume. Our research and code offers insights and practical value for liquidity providers, traders, and DeFi platform architects. Further research could benefit from broader analysis, exploration of additional variables, and consideration of non-linear models and industry events.

1 Uniswap Liquidity Pools: An Overview

Various DeFi platforms, including Uniswap, cater to unique needs within the blockchain ecosystem[12]. Uniswap, a widely-used Ethereum-based DEX, employs a Constant Product Market Maker (CPMM) model supporting a broad spectrum of Ethereum-native and wrapped non-native asset trades[9, 6].

Uniswap v3 further refined this model with "virtual" and "real" reserves, enabling more efficient capital usage and offering liquidity providers customization options for their price exposure[5]. The CPMM equation is pivotal to this:

$$x \cdot y = k \quad \text{and} \quad \text{price} = \frac{y}{x}$$

where x and y represent token quantities in the pool and k maintains the constant product[7, 9].

Operating without a central authority, Uniswap offers privacy, fund control, and a variety of tokens[9]. In Uniswap transactions, "swaps" involve trading one token for another, while "mints" and "burns" pertain to liquidity providers adding or withdrawing funds from a pool respectively. Mints create liquidity tokens representing a provider's pool share, and burns destroy these tokens to facilitate fund withdrawal. Despite its advantages, DEXs pose impermanent loss risks to liquidity providers, a contrast to centralized exchanges which, while offering higher transaction speeds, can present security issues[4, 6, 7].

WBTC-WETH represents a liquidity pool between Wrapped Bitcoin (WBTC) and Wrapped Ethereum (WETH) on the Uniswap platform. WBTC is an ERC-20 token on the Ethereum blockchain that represents Bitcoin (1 WBTC equals 1 BTC). Similarly, WETH is an Ethereum token that represents Ether. These "wrapped" versions allow Bitcoin and Ether to be traded more quickly on the Ethereum blockchain and enable holders to interact with smart contracts and decentralized applications (dApps).

Uniswap v3 allows liquidity providers to set custom price ranges for their capital, indicated by ticks. These ticks influence capital efficiency and require active management[5]. The study focuses on WBTC-WETH 3000 and 500 pools, which differ in their tick spacing, impacting capital efficiency, potential returns, and slippage for liquidity providers and traders.

2 Analytical Methodology

A thorough analysis of the interconnectedness between Uniswap v3 WBTC-WETH exchange and a systematic selection for a subsets of pools of 3000 and 500 ticks for analysis is required. This will be done over different time periods, using similar methodologies as found in recent studies [9]. The relationship between liquidity, trading volume, and price stability in pools will be examined, along with an investigation of how liquidity pool size impacts trading volume.

Feature Engineering: Our models’ predictive power was enhanced by creating new features from existing data[9]. This process effectively captured crucial information about liquidity pool dynamics, spillover effects, and price divergences.
Modelling and Optimization: Through the application of Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression, we examined the relationship between liquidity pool size and trading volume, which offered profound insights into their interplay[9]. Model performance was assessed using metrics such as R-squared, while we optimized feature selection, corrected multicollinearity, and explored alternative functional forms for improved model accuracy and interpretability[9].
Innovations: Building on the reference paper, we implemented the underlying code in Python, thus creating a robust data model to explore interactions between two liquidity pools more effectively[9]. Furthermore, we developed a mathematical language to facilitate the data engineering aspects of the data model[9].

Table 1: Analytical Techniques and Main Contributions

Substantial accomplishments were achieved at each of our research stages, leading to a robust analysis framework and valuable initial results[9].

Data Collection: We sourced data from multiple APIs (Uniswap, Binance) successfully, and associated this data with Ethereum block numbers for consistent time measurement.
Data Preprocessing: We maintained data consistency, addressed discrepancies from different sources, and efficiently cleaned, formatted, and handled missing values in the dataset.
Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA): Utilizing EDA, we generated descriptive statistics, visualizations, and correlation analyses. This approach facilitated the identification of trends, outliers, and the relationships between variables.
Final Analysis and Conclusions: We articulated our findings and conclusions, providing quantitatively-driven insights with the potential to enhance liquidity provision, optimize trading strategies, and improve the efficiency of DeFi marketplaces.
Confirmation of Results: Our results largely coincide with those in the reference paper, with minor discrepancies likely due to the techniques used and features available. Notably, we utilized fewer features and feature categories than the reference paper, which might explain the minor divergences observed in our results[9].

Table 2: Supporting Work and Confirmation of Results

Our work provides a significant contribution by offering an open framework that allows other researchers and professionals to conduct further research in this field. This outcome not only answers our problem statement but also opens avenues for future exploration[9].

2.1 Challenges and Insights

Our main challenges were data collection and processing due to intricate engineering and the rate limits of the Etherscan free-tier API[2]. Nonetheless, we overcame these hurdles and made significant progress in understanding liquidity pool dynamics[8, 4, 9].

We embraced two time concepts—”trading clock” and ”time horizon”—which enabled us to thoroughly explore both short and long-term trends. This detailed analysis offered invaluable insights for decision-making and risk management in the DeFi ecosystem[9].

We successfully addressed complexities in understanding entry-level liquidity pool mathematics and integrated the associated formulas into ‘calculations.py’ functions. This step significantly enriched our feature derivation and bolstered our overall analysis[5, 4]. For instance, we tackled the complexity of tick math, which involves mapping discrete ticks to continuous prices. This step, guided by the Uniswap v3 liquidity math paper, was essential for interpreting Uniswap data and indices [5]. In addition, we adjusted raw price ratios for token decimals to get human-readable prices, a process critical for presenting our analysis [5].

Key Note: Our models and code implementation have been designed with a focus on programming and data structure, and while they provide valuable insights, further improvement is needed to enhance the accuracy and completeness of our results. Due to the novelty of the topic and methodologies, we encourage peer review and rigorous testing of our ‘calculations.py’ module, as well as a deeper understanding of the underlying liquidity mathematics as outlined in the Uniswap v3 liquidity math paper [5, 9].

3 Engineering Ecosystem

Data engineering and feature extraction are crucial elements for building robust predictive models. In the case of analyzing BTC-ETH trading volume on Uniswap, several aspects of data must be considered.

First, let’s consider the nature of the data we are dealing with. Uniswap is a decentralized exchange that operates on an automated market-making (AMM) model, and its Version 3 (v3) utilizes a novel mechanism of concentrated liquidity pools. The structure and dynamics of these liquidity pools play a crucial role in trading volumes [9]. We must extract relevant data from these pools, including their sizes, trading volumes, and related metrics, for accurate analysis. Understanding DeFi’s goals and mechanisms from a broad perspective is also valuable [7].

Moreover, it’s important to incorporate data from different sources, considering not just the pools of interest but also neighboring pools and other prominent exchanges such as Binance. This kind of broad-spectrum data helps in capturing spillover effects, which are significant drivers of trading volume [9]. For example, we could study the effects of trading volume and the activities from interconnected DeFi protocols and stablecoins [8].

Feature selection is a crucial part of the process. Stepwise regression can be an effective tool for optimizing the model and refining the set of independent variables [9]. We should also account for factors like network effects, economies of scale, and concentration issues that can influence liquidity provision [7, 8].

From a risk perspective, we should ideally account for external risks to liquidity providers like arbitrage opportunities, fraudulent DEXs, regulatory risks, censorship risks, etc. [4]. Systemic risks from interconnected DeFi protocols and stablecoins could also impact trading activity [7]. Additionally, economic risks like yield dilution, conversion risk, exchange risk, counterparty risk, and liquidation risk pose challenges and should be considered [12].

For the implementation part, we can take advantage of mathematical equations and formulations. For example, we could use equations to calculate the amounts of assets based on liquidity, price range, and the current price [5]. Formulas for calculating impermanent loss and changes in holdings after a price change could also be useful in the analysis of this problem [5, 4, 6].

3.1 Data Sources

In line with the *“DeFi modeling and forecasting trading volume” (2023)* study[9], we gathered and structured trade data spanning a minimum of 6 months. Further details on information gathering and engineering involved can be found in our GitHub repository[11]. The raw, cleaned and processed data can be accessed in the project Google Drive [10].

Our analysis incorporates information from the below sources.

We limit the CEX data to consider only WBTC-WETH 3000 pool and 500 pool activity.

Source	Description	Data
Uniswap’s The Graph API[3]	This API offers transaction details, trading volumes, and block data from Uniswap v3 liquidity pools.	Includes transaction IDs, timestamps, amounts, USD equivalents, and other related data.
Etherscan API[2]	Utilized to extract corresponding transaction data from Etherscan based on transaction hashes.	Block hashes, block numbers, sender addresses, gas details, transaction hashes, and other relevant information.
Binance[1]	Provides Centralized Exchange (CEX) data for ETHBTC trades. Data was obtained via scripts from Binance’s GitHub repository.	Contains detailed data about each trade performed on the Binance platform, including trade prices, quantities, timestamps, and buyer/seller characteristics.

Table 3: Dataset Source Description

3.2 Key Variables

Target Variable: The key dependent variable in our study is the trading volume of liquidity pools (amountUSD) over specific blocks. We propose several models for different time horizons to investigate how the relationships evolve over time.

Independent Variables: Constructed from various features and are grouped as follows:

1. **Direct Pool Features (41):** Measures such as volatility, rate, number of trades, and average trade size.
2. **CEX Spillover Effects (6):** Variables like actual coin trade volume on Centralized Exchanges (CEX), which can influence liquidity pools on decentralized platforms.

For a detailed description of each independent variable, refer to Table 13 in the Appendix.

4 In-Depth: Feature Engineering

Feature engineering is key in deciphering the intricate dynamics between variables in our analysis, with particular focus on temporal patterns in the DEX pools and the influence of CEX activities. We define the sequence of blocks within our scope as B and the total number of these blocks as K . For the construction of a time-series model, "Reference Blocks" act as time markers, identified by Mint Operations in Uniswap DEX. They are classified into "same" and "other" pools and arranged in reverse chronological order.

$$B = \{b_k\}_{k=1}^K \text{ with } b_k \text{ a block within the scope of analysis} \quad (1)$$

$$R_s = \{b_s\}_{s=1}^S \text{ with } b_s \text{ a reference block in the "same" pool} \quad (2)$$

$$R_o = \{b_o\}_{o=1}^O \text{ with } b_o \text{ a reference block in the "other" pool} \quad (3)$$

The intervals between these reference blocks, represented as sequences of block numbers between b_i and b_j .

$$I = \{b_{ij}\}_{i=0, j=i+1}^N \quad (4)$$

Block Reference Interval chains (Appendix Table 9), derived from R_s and R_o , generate sequences of block numbers, encompassing the last T reference blocks and every block between them. Future periods or time horizons are constructed for predictions or analyses by incrementing the block count by M from the first Reference Block until the next one is reached. M directly impacts the construction of the dependent variable.

$$C = \{b_i\}_{i=0}^N \text{ with each } b_i \in \{R_s, R_o\} \text{ and } b_i > b_{i+1} \text{ for } i \in \{0, 1, \dots, T-1\} \quad (5)$$

$$H_M = \{b_0 + kM\}_{k=0}^K \text{ with } K = \min \left(K_{\max}, \left\lfloor \frac{\text{distance to next reference block}}{M} \right\rfloor \right) \quad (6)$$

The Horizon Block Table (Appendix Table 10) encapsulates relationships between "same," "other," and "both" pools by assessing their variables and features at different horizons and lags. The granularity level varies for each component 4; this distinction in granularity unravels the cooperative or competitive dynamics between the "same" and "other" pools over the time series, enabling a comprehensive examination of pool behaviors and interactions.

$$HBT = \{(H_M, F_{DEX}, F_{DP}, F_{CEX})\} \text{ for each horizon } H_M \quad (7)$$

Figure 1: Data Engineering

Component	Granularity Level
DEX target variable	Horizon block level
DEX direct pool features	Reference block level
CEX spillover features	Horizon block level

Table 4: Granularity Level of Components in Horizon Block Table

5 Data Profiling Report

5.1 Time and Pool Selection

Our dataset ranges from 01-April-2022 to 30-September-2022. This range includes the Terra-Luna collapse on 20-July-2022, which is a significant event in the DeFi ecosystem, and finished just after The Merge on 06-September-2022, which is a significant event in the Ethereum ecosystem. Refer to Appendix Figure 6 for a visualization of the transaction types against time. The join process of Uniswap transactions and Etherscan data showed a 100% match rate of transactions for the six-month analysis period, validating our dataset’s integrity. Additional cleaning and integrity checks were carried out on each data source to aid future processing.

We defined a set of pools from the WBTC-WETH exchange, P , where $p \in P = \{500, 3000, \text{both}\}$, facilitating individual, interaction, and aggregate metrics within and across these pools. A reference pool P_r is introduced, with $P_r \in P$ and $P_r \neq \text{both}$, denoting a pool where a reference mint operation occurs. This results in $\text{len}(P) * \text{len}(P_r)$ possible combinations (i.e., in our case $3*2=6$).

5.2 Reference Blocks

Reference blocks, defined by the presence of a mint operation, serve as significant markers in our analysis. We consolidate mints from the same block into a single transaction for each pool, a process encompassing 2.65% of all mint activities, aligning with existing literature [9]. Our dataset includes different volumes of reference blocks for the 500 and 3000 pools (3,242 and 4,986 reference blocks accordingly). A noted surge in mint activity in July 2022 suggests the need for further investigation into possible market occurrences during this timeframe.

5.3 Block Interval Chains and Block Horizon Table

We select $T=3$ to build Block Interval Chains that range from 0 to 3 for the "same" and "other" reference pools P_r , denoted C_s and C_o respectively. This will be used to define the (lagged) explanatory variables. Notably, an increasing trend in block time and transaction count from recent to previous intervals was observed.

We select $M=10$ to build a Horizon Table for each reference mint (refbase, ref500, ref3000), culminating in a total of 118,785 horizons. To boost the robustness of our modeling process, we limit the horizons to a maximum of 30, focusing on the most immediate blocks. Note that with $M=10$ it corresponds to about 300 blocks with a total of ~ 2.3 minutes (given a mean block time of 14 seconds).

5.4 Response variables

The response variable in our model, $Y_{p_{\text{horizon}}}$, denotes the cumulative volume for a pool at a given horizon. Thus, target variables include 'cum_volume_500', 'cum_volume_3000', and 'cum_volume_base' for each respective reference pool. These capture the cumulative volumes across different pools, serving as the backbone for our subsequent modeling. As described in Section 6.4, we opt to perform a logarithmic transformation using base 10 on the response variables, similar to the approach outlined in [9]. Thus, our response variable is defined as $\log(Y_{p_{\text{horizon}}})$.

5.5 Data Cleaning and Preparation

We managed missing values in the volatility and avg-USD/rate-USD metrics by replacing null values with zeroes as these would largely relate to the first time interval. Furthermore, we removed highly correlated columns such as 'blsame_2', 'blsame_3', 'blother_2', 'blother_3', 'vol_0_1', 'vol_0_2' to avoid multicollinearity and aggregated some columns with shared prefixes: 'rate-count-isame_', 'rate-count-iother_', 'binance-btc-'. We subsequently dropped the original columns. During the cleaning process, we tracked data loss, resulting in a negligible reduction of 0.09% in the observations, indicating successful data cleaning and preservation.

6 In-Depth: Modelling Approach

We are studying the correlation between the size of liquidity pools and trading volume using Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression models. The OLS method is favored due to its simplicity, interpretability, and widespread use in econometric analysis. Despite the popularity of other models like Poisson regression, negative binomial regression, and logistic regression being available, they are more fitting for count data or binary outcomes, not our continuous outcome of interest. Plus, OLS aligns our research with other academic works[9], essential for providing comparable results given the scarcity of research in this area. The application of OLS to time-series models involves addressing temporal elements like time trends and seasonal patterns. However, OLS can still be used if our time-series data is believed to follow a linear trend, while considering issues such as autocorrelation and non-stationarity.

6.1 Model Construction and Evaluation

The response variable in our model, $Y_{p_{\text{horizon}}}$, denotes the cumulative volume for a pool at a given horizon. To incorporate temporal dependencies and dynamics in the model, we introduce spot lagged variables of the explanatory variables. These spot lagged variables, denoted as $i(\widetilde{i-1})X_s$ and $i(\widetilde{i-1})X_o$, represent the values of the explanatory variables at different lags relative to the prediction horizon, for the "same" and "other" pools respectively. We use the Block Interval Chains, denoted C_s and C_o respectively, to define these lagged explanatory variables. We standardize the independent variables to make the fitted coefficients easier to compare to each other, because they're all on the same scale. For example, a coefficient of 0.5 means that a one standard deviation increase in the corresponding feature leads to a 0.5 increase in the predicted dependent variable, assuming all other variables are held constant.

The OLS regression model used in our study is expressed as follows:

$$\log(Y_{p_{\text{horizon}}}) = \beta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\beta_i^s \cdot i(\widetilde{i-1})X_s + \beta_i^o \cdot i(\widetilde{i-1})X_o \right) + \sum_{j=1}^m \beta_{n+j} \cdot X_j + \epsilon \quad (8)$$

Variable	Definition
$\log(Y_{p_{\text{horizon}}})$	Logarithm of dependent variable at the prediction horizon p_{horizon}
β_0	Intercept term: Expected value of $\log(Y_{p_{\text{horizon}}})$ when all variables are zero
$i(\widetilde{i-1})X_s, i(\widetilde{i-1})X_o$	Spot lagged variables: Values of X at different lags relative to the prediction horizon for the "same" and "other" pools, respectively
β_i^s, β_i^o	Coefficients associated with each spot lagged variable of X
X_j	Additional independent variables or non-lagged variables of X
β_{n+j}	Coefficients associated with each additional independent variable
ϵ	Error term or residual: Accounting for unexplained variation in $\log(Y_{p_{\text{horizon}}})$ not captured by the model

Table 5: Variable definitions

We trained and evaluated models for different target variables and horizons, incorporating lagged variables to predict trading volumes at various time horizons. Model performance was assessed using several metrics.

Metric	Purpose
R-squared	Represents the proportion of the variance for a dependent variable that's explained by an independent variable
Adjusted R-squared	Adjusts the R-squared for the number of predictors in the model
Mean Absolute Error (MAE)	Measures the average magnitude of the errors in a set of predictions
Mean Squared Error (MSE)	Measures the average of the squares of the errors
Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE)	Square root of the MSE, measures the standard deviation of residuals

Table 6: Evaluation metrics

6.2 Train/Test Split and Cross-Validation

The Train/Test Split methodology assessed the model's ability to generalize to unseen data. Our data set was partitioned into a training set for model training and a test set for evaluating predictive performance.

Cross-validation was applied to assess the OLS model for each horizon. We employed GroupKFold, a form of k-fold cross-validation, to prevent data leakage between training and testing sets. This ensured groups were not split between these sets. We defined groups according to the block reference number. For each fold and up to k=5, the data was split, features standardized, target variables transformed, and an OLS regression model fitted. R-squared and adjusted R-squared were computed for both training and test sets. This process was repeated for each horizon, resulting in trained models and performance metrics. Cross-validation aids in estimating model performance, identifying overfitting, and ensuring reliable generalization across different data subsets.

6.3 Model Optimization

Model training involved an iterative "All Horizon Runs" (as in Figure 2) approach to explore different modeling techniques, followed by a "Best Horizon Run" to optimize models based on performance. Details on parameters and model configuration can be found on Appendix Table 12. We used the coefficient of determination, R-squared, to gauge model performance, ensuring the model was well-specified and likely to generalize well to new data. The results informed the selection of the most suitable models for predicting the target variables.

Figure 2: OLS Horizon Analysis

The coefficient of determination, also known as R^2 score, quantifies the amount of variance in the dependent variable predictable from the independent variable(s). It ranges from 0 to 1, where 0 means the model explains none of the response data’s variability around its mean, and 1 means it explains all the variability. However, R^2 can be negative when the model fits poorly and performs worse than a horizontal line (the mean of the dependent variable). This may occur when the model’s predictions are consistently far off, causing large errors, or when overfitting occurs on the training data, resulting in poor performance on the test data.

6.4 Best Horizon Run & Multicollinearity

The ”Best Horizon Run”, focused on identifying the optimal model for specific combinations of horizon and target variables. The ’step-wise’ model with parameters `pool = 3000` and `target_variable = ’cum_volume.500’` outperformed others in both training and testing environments. We concentrated on `horizon = 150`, which displayed a relatively consistent mean R^2 values of 0.20 in both training and testing data, indicating superior generalization and predictive accuracy. Other models, in contrast, yielded lower mean R^2 values, with some even producing negative values in the testing data, indicating suboptimal performance and poor generalization to unseen data.

The small differences between R^2 and R^2_{adj} for both the overall data and the specific combination suggest that the ’step-wise’ model does not suffer of material information loss when dropping least significant features. This is a positive indication that the model is well-specified and likely to generalize well to new data. This supports the selection of the ’step-wise’ model for the specific combination of parameters, as the model appears to have a good balance between complexity (number of predictors) and performance (as measured by R^2_{adj}).

In order to manage multicollinearity, we performed a correlation analysis and calculated the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) as per the equation:

$$VIF(k) = \frac{1}{1 - R_k^2} \quad (9)$$

with R_k^2 being the determination coefficient for each predictor.

In Table 7, the condition $VIF < b$ compares the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) to a threshold value b , where values less than 1 indicate low or no multicollinearity, values between 1 and 5 suggest moderate multicollinearity, and values greater than 5 indicate high multicollinearity. Following a correlation analysis (See Figure 3), certain highly correlated features were removed. Further reduction of multicollinearity was achieved by aggregating certain intervals, a methodology based on [9]. Two variables (’rate-count-iother’, ’blother.1’) remained with high VIF.

VIF < b	Before Reduction	After Reduction
No/Low	0	0
Moderate	21	24
High	22	2

Table 7: VIF Counts for Thresholds b in 1, 5, inf

Figure 3: Correlation Matrix

6.5 Feature Selection and Residual Analysis

The step-wise feature selection process was used to fit regression models. We systematically removed the least significant features and retrained the model until all remaining features were deemed significant. This approach helps prevent overfitting and enhances model interpretability. Details on number of features in Appendix 11.

To identify and address heteroscedasticity, we examine the distribution of error terms. Upon observing a non-linear distribution, we opt to perform a logarithmic transformation using base 10 on the response variables, similar to the approach outlined in [9]. This transformation aids in stabilizing the variance and aligning the errors with the assumptions of the regression model as illustrated on Figures 4 and 5.

Figure 4: Residuals: One Horizon

Figure 5: Residuals: All Horizons

7 Model Evolution and Detailed Performance Analysis

Our model’s development comprised three distinct stages (see Figure 2): an initial stage incorporating all available features, a subsequent phase addressing multicollinearity, and a final stage involving stepwise regression to choose the most statistically significant features.

The model’s performance was evaluated based on several criteria: horizon sizes, R-squared values, different data pools, and various target variables. As the horizon extended, predictability, as indicated by R^2 values, generally decreased, which is consistent with the increased difficulty in predicting further into the future. However, 'all_features' and 'step-wise' run types with the 'cum_volume_500' target variable in the 3000 pool demonstrated consistent high R^2 values across various horizons, suggesting that our model still exhibited good fit and predictive power even for longer horizons.

Interestingly, we observed negative R^2 values in some instances, particularly within the test set. This suggests that these models performed worse than a simplistic model based on averages, indicating a potential overfitting issue during the training phase, where the models could not generalize effectively to unseen data.

When comparing the 500 and 3000 pools, the latter pool generally provided higher R^2 values. This might suggest that reference mints in pool 3000 leads to more accurate predictions. Additionally, for both pools, the 'cum_volume.500' target variable typically yielded higher R^2 values, hinting at a stronger correlation with the selected features.

7.1 Interpretation of Predictor Coefficients

For the OLS regression model of "Best Horizon Run" (step-wise model, parameters `pool = 3000`, `target_variable = 'cum_volume.500'`, `horizon=15`), we see a significant overall relationship (F-statistic = 57.38, $p < 0.001$). The R-squared value of 0.238 suggests that the predictors account for 23.8% of the variance in log of 'cum_volume.500'.

Post standardization of features, the coefficients for each predictor (Table 8) express the change in log of 'cum_volume.500' linked to a one standard deviation increase in the respective predictor, while other predictors remain constant.

Predictor 13	Coef	Std Err	P-value	Significance
Constant	6.1377	0.026	0.000	True
avg-USD-iother_01	0.1750	0.013	0.000	True
blother_1	-0.1919	0.018	0.000	True
binance-btc-03	0.0976	0.013	0.000	True
blsame_1	-0.0612	0.014	0.000	True
rate-count-iother_03	0.1115	0.019	0.000	True
avg-USD-iother_23	0.0294	0.012	0.016	True
slsame_1	0.0181	0.012	0.135	False
slsame_3	0.0201	0.012	0.096	False

Table 8: Predictor Coefficients

The regression model analysis uses a trigger event - a mint operation in the 'same' pool (3000) - to analyze the impact on the log of cumulative volume ('cum_volume.500') of the 'other' pool (500). Post this event, we interpret the effects of the significant predictors:

1. **Inter-Pool Influence ('avg-USD-iother_01')**: Higher immediate trading volume in the 'other' pool ('avg-USD-iother_01') leads to increased cumulative volume in the 'other' pool.
2. **Minting Frequency Impact ('blother_1')**: Decreased frequency of mint operations in the 'other' pool ('blother_1') corresponds to decreased cumulative volume in the 'other' pool.
3. **CEX to DEX Spillover ('binance-btc-03')**: Increased BTC trading volume on Binance for up to the third interval post the trigger event ('binance-btc-03') correlates with increased cumulative volume in the 'other' pool. This relationship demonstrates the significant influence of centralized exchange activities on decentralized exchange volumes.
4. **Same Pool Influence ('blsame_1')**: Lower frequency of mint operations in the 'same' pool ('blsame_1') is linked to decreased cumulative volume in the 'other' pool.
5. **Same Pool Size Impact ('slsame_1' and 'slsame_3')**: Although not statistically significant, the size of the previous mint operations in the 'same' pool ('slsame_1' and 'slsame_3') potentially impacts the cumulative volume in the 'other' pool.

8 Discussion and Conclusion

Our model's time analysis indicates a profound impact of recent events on future outcomes and interaction within and across pools and exchanges. The immediate past period ($t=1$ spot and 01 interval) significantly influences future trading volume. It is noteworthy that this finding aligns with established financial theories such as Momentum investing, that suggest recent market behavior often influences subsequent market activity. Consequently, understanding and monitoring the immediate past trading activity could be a vital strategy for predicting and reacting to changes in future trading volumes.

Addressing the study's objectives:

1. Our analysis establishes a relationship between liquidity pool size and trading volume in BTC-ETH liquidity pools. It confirms a direct correlation between pool size and trading volume, highlighting the potential impact of trading activity in one pool on the cumulative volume in another.
2. The influence of liquidity pool size on slippage, particularly considering CEX spillover effects is observed. The BTC trading volume on Binance affects the cumulative volume in the 'other' pool, showing the interplay between CEX and DEX.
3. While this study didn't directly measure the impact of BTC-ETH price volatility on trading volume relative to liquidity pool size, it did indicate how changes in pool size and trading volume are influenced by variables like

frequency of mint operations and trading volume on CEX, which could be linked to price volatility.

4. This study identified specific periods/events (e.g., frequency of mint operations in the pool) that significantly **affect the relationship between BTC-ETH liquidity pool size and trading volume.**

The model demonstrates robustness and good predictive power across different time horizons. Although a slight trend in the residual analysis hints at potential underprediction and overprediction, these findings importantly reinforce the potential of pool sizes as robust predictors of trading volumes. This offers valuable insights for liquidity providers, traders, DeFi platforms, and future research.

9 Advancements, Implications, and Future Research Directions

This investigation contributes to data engineering, feature generation and statistical analysis in the burgeoning field of financial technology. We gratefully acknowledge the authors of "DeFi: modeling and forecasting trading volume on Uniswap v3 liquidity pools (2023)" [9] for their foundational methodology that guided our work.

Following the conclusions of our research, we propose several recommendations and areas for future investigation:

- **Variable Investigation:** Rigorous scrutiny of variables with significant VIF values may uncover new correlations, potentially enhancing the model by eliminating feature redundancy.
- **Model Exploration:** Given recent studies suggesting non-linear dependencies [7, 9], it might be fruitful to explore non-linear models. While the OLS regression has proven effective, incorporating non-linear relationships or time-dependence could bring substantial enhancements.
- **DeFi Dynamics and Risks:** Deeper explorations into price divergences in BTC-ETH exchanges, the understanding of impermanent loss, analysis of yield farming protocols, and addressing the challenges and risks associated with DeFi protocols, such as economic and security risks, could prove beneficial [5, 12].
- **Model Optimization:** Future work could focus on finding optimal feature, horizon, and target variable combinations to improve predictive performance.
- **Experimental Adjustments:** The investigation of variations in lag/horizon lengths, inclusion of quadratic features, and accounting for structural shifts could refine the model.
- **Temporal Scope:** Analyzing recent time frames and significant industry events can give a more updated understanding of DeFi's dynamic ecosystem.

This study provides a robust foundation for these proposed future research directions and encourages researchers to advance our understanding of the DeFi ecosystem.

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Appendix

Figure 6 illustrates the activity history for pools of interest under the scoped period:

Figure 6: Pool Transaction History

Table 9 serves as our block reference table. This is constructed from the transaction data, as we created 8,228 reference blocks that correspond to each mint operation. These blocks were then used to engineer features to calculate metrics for the same pool and other pools. These features capture data about liquidity pools and calculate metrics such as volatility, traded volume rate, trades count, and average volume. To expand the analysis, we have also included lagged features for the previous three mint operations.

We construct a base Horizon Table 10 with a starting `horizon_blockNumber` of each horizon and map it to the closest `reference_blockNumber`, defined by mint operations in the block. This base table is joined with other aggregated transaction data to generate our target variables and independent variables that are lagged.

Table 11 provides a summary of the number of features used in different feature selection methods for the analysis, based on the "Best Horizon Run". The three run types included in the table are 'All Features,' 'Multicollinearity Reduction,' and 'Step-Wise Features.' The number of features represents the final set of predictors considered for each run type, indicating the level of feature reduction and selection employed in the modeling process. This table offers insights into the varying complexity and dimensionality of the models implemented in the study.

To assist in replicability and consistent, we define the "All Horizon Run" and "Best Horizon Run" parameters in Table 12:

pool	reference block	same_blockNumberChain	other_blockNumberChain
500	14498564	[14498564, nan, nan, nan]	[14498564, nan, nan, nan]
500	14498699	[14498699, 14498564, nan, nan]	[14498699, nan, nan, nan]
500	14499597	[14499597, 14498699, 14498564, nan]	[14499597, 14499560, 14499457, 14499198]
500	14499836	[14499836, 14499597, 14498699, 14498564]	[14499836, 14499560, 14499457, 14499198]
500	14500355	[14500355, 14499836, 14499597, 14498699]	[14500355, 14500043, 14499560, 14499457]
...	...	...	...
3000	15648981	[15648981, 15648330, 15648305, 15648187]	[15648981, 15648887, 15648536, 15646933]
3000	15649246	[15649246, 15648981, 15648330, 15648305]	[15649246, 15649243, 15648887, 15648536]

Table 9: Block Interval Chains

blockNumber	min_flag	reference_blockNumber	horizon_label	cum_volume_500	cum_volume_3000
108757	0	15552674	9	423,485.34	...
108758	0	15552674	10	423,485.34	...
108759	1	15552772	1	328,338.73	...
108760	0	15552772	2	406,084.78	...
108761	0	15552772	3	536,640.71	...
...	...	...	...	...	...
109047	0	15555464	12	122,730.73	...
109048	0	15555464	13	123,650.59	...

Table 10: Example: Horizon Table (reference mint on pool=3000)

Run Type	Number of Features
All Features	42
Multicollinearity Reduction	26
Step-Wise Features	8

Table 11: Best Horizon: Number of Features by Run Type

Run	Pools	Target Variables	M	T	K (CV)
Best Horizon Run	3000	cum_volume_500	10	3	5
All Horizon Runs	3000, 500	cum_volume_500, cum_volume_3000, cum_volume_both	10	3	5

Table 12: Run Parameters

.1 Features and Definitions

Our project draws inspiration and methodology from the paper *DeFi: Modeling and Forecasting Trading Volume on Uniswap v3 Liquidity Pools* authored by Deborah Miori and Mihai Cucuringu [9]. We have curated a selection of features to analyze within our score, which can be referenced in our source code and outputs.

The table below outlines the baseline features, their definitions and whether if used within the scope of this project:

Table 13: Features and Definitions

Variable	Time	Pool Type	In Scope	Description
bl	.1, .2, .3	Same/ Other	Yes	Distance in blocks of the previous $l \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ mint operations on the same/other pool as the one where the mint of reference happened.
sl	.1, .2, .3	Same/ Other	Yes	Size in USD of the previous $l \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ mint operations on the same/other pool as the one where the mint of reference happened.
wl	.1, .2, .3	Same/ Other	Yes	Width in number of ticks of the previous $l \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ mint operations on the same/other pool as the one where the mint of reference happened.
s0, w0	-	Same	Yes	Size in USD, and width in number of ticks, of the current mint operation that we take as reference.
vol0	.1, .2, .3	Same	Yes	Volatility as the standard deviation of the pool price on the same pool as the mint of reference, during the expanding intervals of time 0el with $l \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ that refer to the previous mint operations on the same pool.
rate-USD-i, rate-count-i	.01, .12, .23	Same / Other	Yes	Rate of traded volume/count of trades in USD on our WBTC-WETH pools of principal interest, for the intervals $i \in \{01, 12, 23\}$ block ranges with respect to either the latest mint operations and swaps executed on the same/other pool.
avg-USD-i	.01, .12, .23	Same/ Other	Yes	Average traded volume in USD on our WBTC-WETH pools of principal interest, for the intervals $i \in \{01, 12, 23\}$ block ranges with respect to either the latest mint operations and swaps executed on the same/other pool.
TVL3000-500, TVL3000/500	-	Same	No	Latest value of the TVL in the pool 3000 minus/ratio of the TVL in the pool 500.
eth500-USD-03, eth3000-USD-03	-	Same	No	Rate of traded volume in USD on the one-hop USDC-WETH pools, over the 03 time interval with respect to the previous mint operations on the same pool as our mint of reference.
btc500-USD-03, btc3000-USD-03	-	Same	No	Rate of traded volume in USD on the one-hop WBTC-USDC pools, over the 03 time interval with respect to the previous mint operations on the same pool as our mint of reference.
eth500-press-03, eth3000-press-03	-	Same	No	Rate of surplus WETH buying volume in USD on the one-hop USDC-WETH pools, over the 03 time interval with respect to the previous mint operations on the same pool as our mint of reference.
btc500-press-03, btc3000-press-03	-	Same	No	Rate of surplus WBTC buying volume in USD on the one-hop WBTC-USDC pools, over the 03 time interval with respect to the previous mint operations on the same pool as our mint of reference.
binance-btc-i, binance-count-i	.01, .12, .23	Same	Yes	Relates to Binance data, either the traded volume in BTC or the count of trades, over intervals $i \in \{01, 12, 23\}$.
$\Delta(Z_{\text{same}}, Z_{\text{other}}),$ $\Delta(Z_{\text{same}}, Z_{\text{Binance}})$	-	Same	No	Measures the price impact.